

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2023 NOVI SAD**

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2023 NOVI SAD**

31st of March 2023 :

Diagnostic and therapeutic principles in dental medicine I

1st of April 2023 :

Diagnostic and therapeutic principles in dental medicine II

CIP - Каталогизacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Matice srpske, Novi Sad

616.31(082)

The INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference in Dentistry (2023 ; Novi Sad)

Proceedings of The International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2023, 31st of March-
1st of April 2023, Novi Sad [Elektronski izvor] / editor Milica Jeremić Knežević. - Novi
Sad : Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina, 2023

Način pristupa (URL): <https://www.simpozijumstomatologa.rs/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/2023-Proceedings.pdf>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan
11.4.2023. - Nasl. sa naslovnog ekrana. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-80894-06-5

a) Stomatologija -- Zbornici

COBISS.SR-ID 113768969

**Organization of this Conference was approved by the Scientific
Council of the Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina**

Editor: Dr Milica Jeremić Knežević, professor

Publisher: Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina

Organizing committee

Prof. dr Tatjana Puškar- president

Prof. dr Sanja Vujkov

Dr Marko Gojnić

Dr Milojko Jovanović

Stevan Dragosavljević, MCS

Prof. dr Aleksandra Maletin

Prof. dr Duška Blagojević

Prof. dr Ivan Šarčev

Prof. dr Siniša Mirković

Prof. dr Branislav Bajkin

Prof. dr Ivana Gušić

Prof. dr Bojana Milekić

Teach. Asist. dr Jelena Komšić

Teach. Asist. dr Mirjana Stojšić

Scientific committee

Prof. dr Milica Jeremić Knežević- president (RS)

Prof. dr Igor Budak (RS)

Prof. dr Larisa Blažić (RS)

Prof. dr Đorđe Vukelić (RS)

Prof. dr Bojan Petrović (RS)

Prof. dr Mirjana Bošković (RS)

Prof. dr Anca Jivanescu (RO)

Prof. dr Davor Seifert (CRO)

Prof. dr Jozsef Szalma (HU)

Prof. dr Rebeka Rudolf (SLO)

Prof. dr Zamri Radzi (MAL)

Prof. dr Dominic Eggbeer (UK)

Prof. dr Dubravka Marković (RS)

Dr Petar Ninkov (NOR)

Assist. Prof. dr Branka Trifković (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Daniela Đurović Koprivica (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Iva Milinković (RS)

Assist. Prof. dr Ana Todorović (RS)

Assist Prof. dr Dušica Simić Panić (RS)

On behalf of the Organizing and Scientific Committee, we are pleased to welcome you all at the International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2023 Novi Sad.

The Scientific and Organization Committee made an effort to make a conference that has scientific value and is also interesting for dental professionals, although it is held in hybrid form.

You will meet an exceptional program covering different topics, from basic research areas to areas within daily practice of Restorative Dentistry, Endodontics, Prosthodontics, Oral Surgery and Implantology, Periodontology, Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry.

*President of the Organizing Committee
Prof. dr Tatjana Puskar*

*President of the Scientific Committee
Prof. dr Milica Jeremic Knezevic*

TABLE OF CONTENTS

FULL PAPERS LECTURERS.....	6
BIOACTIVE MATERIALS IN DENTAL PULP THERAPY.....	7
STATE OF THE ART AND DEVELOPMENT OF GOLD DENTAL ALLOYS FROM ZLATARNA CELJE.....	12
ROLE OF PHYSICAL THERAPY IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA ...	19
SINGLE POSTERIOR IMPLANTS IMMEDIATE LOADING BY MEANS OF ONE ABUTMENT ONE TIME.....	23
DENTAL-PROSTHETIC RESTORATION IN SEMI-MOBILE AND IMMOBILE GERIATRIC PATIENTS IN CONDITIONS OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC.....	28
IN VITRO ACCURACY EVALUATION OF THREE DIFFERENT SCANNING PROTOCOLS....	33
CHAIRSIDE CAD/CAM RESTORATIONS: WHERE IS THE LIMIT?.....	38
DENTAL PLAQUE AND SALIVA MICROBIOME. DO WE KNOW ENOUGH ABOUT THEM?43	
USE OF PIDAQ IN A SOCIODENTAL APPROACH FOR ESTIMATING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT NEED.....	47
MANAGEMENT OF DEEP CARIES: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES.....	53
DENTURE STOMATITIS AND OTHER CANDIDA–ASSOCIATED INFECTIONS IN THE ORAL CAVITY.....	58
EPIDEMIOLOGY OD HEPATIS C IN SPLIT-DALMATIA COUNTY.....	61
SOST AND DKK-1 AS BIOMARKERS FOR TREATMENT OUTCOMES OF CHRONIC STATIN THERAPY IN PERIODONTAL DISEASE.....	66
PERIODONTITIS AS A RISK FACTOR FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SYSTEMIC DISEASES	70
ADVANCES IN MODERN PREVENTIVE DENTISTRY.....	74
FROM PERIODONTAL HEALTH TO DISEASE: THE IMPACT OF SMOKING.....	81
APPLICATION OF CELL CULTURES IN DENTAL RESEARCH.....	85
VISTA - VESTIBULAR APPROACH IN PERIODONTAL AND PERI-IMPLANT SOFT TISSUE REGENERATION.....	90
DIODE LASERS IN DENTISTRY, DENTIN HYPERSENSITIVITY - THE BEST THERAPEUTIC APPROACH.....	96
PROBIOTIC SUPPLEMENTATION IN DENTAL CARIES PREVENTION.....	101
PREVENTION OF DENTAL CARIES IN CHILDREN.....	107
BIOMECHANICAL ASPECTS OF IMPLANT PROSTHODONTICS.....	111
REVIEW OF MODERN ROOT CANAL FILLING MATERIALS.....	116
SCREENING FOR LOSSES IN INTRINSIC CAPACITY OF OLDER PEOPLE IN THE DENTAL PRACTICE.....	122
COMPUTER ASSISTED OCCLUSAL ANALYSIS IN IMPLANT DENTISTRY.....	123
HOW TO PERFORM CORONECTOMY OF WISDOM TEETH? DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC TIPS AND TRICKS.....	124

CYTOKINES AS MOLECULAR PAIN BIOMARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH TEMPOROMANDIBULAR DISORDER.....	125
CLINICAL ORIENTATION OF THE OCCLUSAL PLANE USING A MODIFICATION OF THE BALKWILL ANGLE	126
FULL PAPERS.....	127
ADVANCED TECHNIQUE FOR SMILE DESIGN IN PROSTHODONTICS AND AESTHETIC DENTISTRY	128
ABSTRACTS.....	132
ODONTODISPLASIA - CASE REPORT	133
PAROTID GLAND SWELLING AFTER CHLORHEXIDINE MOUTHRINSE: CASE REPORT .	134
THERAPY OF PSEUDOPROGENIA IN MIXED DENTITION	135
DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT.....	136
THE CORRECT INDICATION – BASIC PRECONDITION IN DIASTEMA THERAPY	137
DYNAMICS OF FLUORIDE ION RELEASE FROM TWO CONVENTIONAL GLAS-IONOMER CEMENTS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY	138
COMBINATION OF FULL- AND SPLIT-THICKNESS CORONALLY DISPLACED FLAP WITH CONNECTIVE TISSUE GRAFT IN THE GINGIVAL RECESSION TREATMENT	139
IMPROVEMENT OF THE HYBRID LAYER MORPHOLOGY BY DENTINAL COLLAGEN CROSS-LINKERS.....	140
COST ACTION 21122- PROMOTING GERIATRIC MEDICINE IN COUNTRIES WHERE IT IS STILL EMERGING. (PROGRAMMING).....	141
THERAPY OF DISTAL BITE BY TWIN BLOCK APPLIANCE.....	143
APPLICATION OF SPHERICAL TiO ₂ NANOPARTICLES AS MODIFICATION OF GLASS-IONOMER CEMENTS	144
KNOWLEDGE OF DENTISTS AND PHYSICIANS ABOUT THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PERIODONTITIS AND SYSTEMIC DISEASES.....	145
LIP PRINT PATTERN AS AN IDENTIFICATION TOOL	146
BIOLOGICALLY BASED THERAPIES IN ENDODONTICS - LATEST STANDPOINTS FOR VITAL PULP THERAPY.....	147
ORAL MUCOSAL LESIONS IN CHILDREN	148
THERAPY PLANNING FOR SUCOMPLETELY EDENTULOUS PATIENTS.....	149
TESTS FOR INVESTIGATION OF CYTOTOXICITY IN DENTISTRY.....	150
FREQUENCY OF RUBBER DAM USE AMONG DENTIST IN SERBIA AND REGION.....	151

BIOLOGICALLY BASED THERAPIES IN ENDODONTICS - LATEST STANDPOINTS FOR VITAL PULP THERAPY

Vukoje K.¹, Ramić B.¹, Kantardžić I.¹, Cvjetičanin M.¹, Stojšin I.^{1,2}, Mirnić J.¹, Veljović T.¹, Maletin A.¹

¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Department of Dental Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

²Dental Clinic of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract:

Introduction: Vital pulp therapy (VPT) techniques for years were means for preservation of the radicular pulp in immature adult teeth. Today, according to the latest position statement of the European Society of Endodontology (ESE) from 2019 and American Association of Endodontists (AAE) from 2021, the focus of VPT is broader; including teeth previously thought to have irreversibly inflamed pulps.

Rationale: Maintaining the health and vitality of the pulp, preventing apical periodontitis and developing minimally invasive biologically based therapies became important themes within contemporary clinical endodontics. The current AAE diagnostic terminology assigns a vital pulp to one of three categories: normal pulp, reversible or irreversible pulpitis (which could be symptomatic or asymptomatic). Based on clinical, biological and theoretical considerations, there is no clear boundary for the irreversibility of the pulpal disease and according to this even symptomatic pulps may be candidates for VPT. More precise gradation suggests the following terminology: initial, mild, moderate and severe pulpitis. This standpoint strongly advise the complete removal of demineralized infected dentin, the use of magnification (especially if the pulp becomes exposed) and the use of biomaterials such as calcium silicate cements in VPT procedures due to their immunomodulatory effects.

Conclusion: There is a need to promote minimally invasive treatment strategies in Operative Dentistry and Endodontology; however, the development of accurate diagnostic tools, evidence-based protocols and education in management of the exposed pulp are critical in the future. The presented position statement also encourages additional clinical trials to assess long-term outcomes of such VPT and a review of the endodontic diagnostic terminology.

Key words: deep caries management, direct pulp capping, endodontics, pulpotomy, vital pulp therapy